

Note on the Formation of a Ruby-red Jelly of Zirconium Sulphosalicylic Acid

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The preparation and properties of zirconium sulphosalicylic acid jellies have already been reported (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 10, 281). It was observed that when a concentrated solution of zirconium oxychloride is added to a strong solution of 5-sulphosalicylic acid, the mixture on standing for some hours sets to transparent or opalescent jellies. The authors have now observed that when zirconium sulphosalicylic acid jelly is allowed to set in presence of aluminium nitrate or nitric acid solution, it begins to develop a reddish tinge after a few hours and by the time of the setting of the jelly it assumes a very fine ruby-red colour. The colour of the jelly is preserved for months.

Different amounts of 50% sulphosalicylic acid (3.99N) were mixed with a solution of zirconium oxychloride, corresponding to 310.68 g. ZrO_2 per litre in presence of 0.914N aluminium nitrate solution and the following observations were made.

TABLE I

Total volume was made up to 5 c.c. by adding water. $ZrOCl_2 = 1$ c.c.

Sulphosalicylic acid.	Aluminium nitrate.	Observations.
2.0 c.c.	0 c.c.	White opalescent jelly in 16 hrs.
2.0	1.0	Slightly pink jelly in 19 hrs.
2.0	1.5	Pink jelly in 21 hrs. with opalescence.
2.5	0.0	White opalescent jelly in 21 hrs.
2.5	1.0	Transparent ruby-red jelly in 23 hrs.
2.5	1.5	Transparent ruby-red jelly in 24 hrs.

TABLE II.

Total volume = 5 c.c.		ZrOCl ₂ = 1 c.c.
Sulphosalicylic acid.	HNO ₃ (1.09N).	Observations.
2.0 c.c.	0 c.c.	White opalescent jelly in 16 hrs.
2.0	1.0	Pink jelly in 40 hrs.
2.0	1.5	Red jelly in 40 hrs.
2.0	2.0	Ruby-red jelly in 50 hrs.
2.5	0	White opalescent jelly in 21 hrs.
2.5	1.0	Ruby-red jelly in 40 hrs.
2.5	1.5	Ruby-red jelly in 40 hrs.

The development of colour has also been studied by Nutting's spectrophotometer in the regions 5400\AA and 6600\AA . For comparison, the results with the jelly to which no aluminium nitrate was added are also given. The jelly was prepared by mixing 3 c. c. of zirconium oxychloride and 4 c. c. of sulphosalicylic acid with 5 c. c. of water in the case of blank jelly and with 5 c.c. of 0.914N aluminium nitrate in the case of ruby-red jelly. Time of the setting of the jelly was 42 hours.

TABLE III.

Time.	Extinction coefficients			
	Colourless jelly.		Red jelly.	
Region →	5400\AA .	6600\AA .	5400\AA .	6600\AA .
0 day	0.10	0.06	0.08	0.04
1	0.11	0.19	0.10	0.04
2	0.11	0.18	0.33	0.15
3	0.16	0.15	0.52	0.15
4	0.23	0.16	0.80	0.17
8	0.25	0.15	1.33	0.17

The results of Table III show that during the course of 8 days, in the jelly to which no aluminium nitrate was added, the absorption in both the regions was almost of the same order, while in the presence of nitrate, the absorption in the red region, 6600\AA , is almost the same as in the case of colourless jelly but the opacity is much developed in the green region 5400\AA .

The colour of the jellies in the case of nitric acid becomes yellowish brown on keeping for a month, while in presence of aluminium nitrate, it remains as such. In presence of sodium nitrate, a jubilant yellow coloured jelly is obtained.